

Studies on thermal behaviors of polyvalent metal ion bound systems

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Manuscript received online 05 June 2013, revised 11 July 2013, accepted 12 July 2013

Abstract : Guar gum is a water soluble natural polymer and its structure is well known. Polyacrylamide is also a water soluble polymer. Aqueous solution of guar gum and polyacrylamide bind polyvalent metal ion in a definite condition. Thermal behaviours for cupric ion bound guar gum and yttrium ion bound guar gum are different from that for guar gum itself. Similarly, thermal behaviours for cupric ion bound polyacrylamide and yttrium ion bound polyacrylamide are different from that for polyacrylamide. The differences in thermal behaviors of polyvalent metal ions with polymer may be explained on the basis of SHAB principle.

Keywords : Natural polymer, polyvalent metal ion, differential scanning calorimetry, TGA.

Introduction

Guar gum and its derivatives are among the most important water soluble polymers and guar gum has also great industrial use¹⁻³. Metal ions are used to cross-link water soluble polymers to produce high-viscosity gels that are used to support and transport solid particles and to block flow channels in underground formations^{4,5}. So thermal behaviors for polyvalent metal ion bound polymer are important. Major drawback of guar gum is its poor biodegradation resistance⁶. When guar gum is grafted with polyacrylamide side chains⁶, resulting graft copolymer becomes considerable biodegradation resistant⁶. But thermal analysis on guar gum-graft-acrylamide and polyvalent metal ion bound guar gum-graft-acrylamide have already been done to understand nature of ion binding and reported⁷⁻⁹. In this present investigation, thermal behaviours for guar gum, polyacrylamide, polyvalent metal ion bound guar gum and polyvalent metal ion bound polyacrylamide have been reported to understand the difference with those using guar gum-graft-acrylamide.

Materials and brief methods :

Guar gum and polyacrylamide were obtained from Rheological Laboratory of Materials Science Centre of IIT, Kharagpur, India. Structure of guar gum is shown in Fig. 1.

Cupric nitrate solution and yttrium nitrate solution can be prepared by dissolving cupric oxide and Y_2O_3 in nitric acid¹⁰.

Fig. 1. Structure of guar gum.

Aqueous solution of guar gum when is mixed with $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution or yttrium nitrate solution and pH of the mixture is raised, a distinct mass separates, which is different from precipitate in appearance which indicates polymer may take part in formation of such distinct mass. **Similar theme happens** by mixing aqueous solution of polyacrylamide and $Cu(NO_3)_2$ solution or $Y(NO_3)_3$ solution and raising pH. pH can be raised by NH_4OH and mass can be suitably washed and dried for **polyvalent metal ions bound soluble polymers**.

Thermal analysis for **all metal ions bound polymers**

along with polymer itself have been carried out by STANTON REDCROFT STA 625 simultaneous thermal analyzer in static air using 4–10 mg sample.

Results and discussion

Plots for differential scanning calorimetric (DSC) analysis and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) for guar gum are shown in Fig. 2. DSC plot indicates more than one exotherm along with weight loss in TGA due to thermal decomposition. DSC and TGA plots for cupric ion bound guar gum (Fig. 3) are different from those for guar gum itself. DSC and TGA plots (Fig. 4) for yttrium ion bound guar gum indicate slight explosive nature. DSC and TGA plots for polyacrylamide are shown in Fig. 5. DSC plot indicates more than one exotherm for thermal decomposition (Fig. 5). This is also supported by TGA plot. But in case of cupric ion bound polyacrylamide (Fig. 6), slight explosive nature is achieved. Surprisingly, in case of yttrium ion bound polyacrylamide (Fig. 7), explosive nature

is not obvious. The probable cause behind this may be explained on the basis of SHAB principle.

Y^{3+} has higher positive charge than Cu^{2+} . So it is expected that Y^{3+} is harder acid than Cu^{2+} . Polyacrylamide contains nitrogen and guar gum contains oxygen. Oxygen has higher electronegativity than nitrogen. So oxygen is harder centre than nitrogen. According to soft and hard acid base principle, hard acid comes in strong interaction with hard base and soft acid with soft base. This is probably the cause for slight explosive nature for yttrium ion bound guar gum and cupric ion bound polyacrylamide.

In Fig. 7, more than one exotherm is achieved in DSC plot but nature of the plot is quite different from that for polyacrylamide itself. Difference in DSC thermograms for yttrium ion bound guar gum and for yttrium ion bound polyacrylamide supports involvement of polymer in the mass. Similarly difference in DSC thermogram for cu-

Fig. 2. Thermogram for guar gum.

Fig. 3. Thermogram for cupric ion bound guar gum.

Fig. 4. Thermogram for yttrium ion bound guar gum.

Fig. 5. Thermogram for polyacrylamide.

Fig. 6. Thermogram for cupric ion bound polyacrylamide.

Fig. 7. Thermogram for yttrium ion bound polyacrylamide.

pric ion bound guar gum and for cupric ion bound polyacrylamide supports involvement of polymer in the mass. Presence of more than one exotherm in DSC thermograms (Figs. 3 and 7) also supports involvement polymer in mass. Almost line like exotherm in DSC thermogram for yttrium ion bound guar gum (Fig. 4) and abnormal rise in TGA plot along with narrow exotherm in DSC plot for cupric ion bound polyacrylamide (Fig. 6) are indicating some explosive nature. These also support involvement of polymer in the mass.

It has been already reported that DSC thermogram for guar gum-graft-acrylamide contains an endotherm at near about 223 °C which can be attributed to cyclic imide formation and acid anhydride formation⁷. So this indicates -COOH group. This -COOH group may appear due to hydrolysis during preparation or storage of the graft co-polymer⁵. This -COOH group will appear in the side

chain of guar gum-graft-acrylamide but not in the backbone. There is no endotherm at 223 °C in DSC thermogram for polyvalent metal ion bound guar gum-graft-acrylamide⁸. This work supports involvement of -COOH group of guar gum-graft-acrylamide for binding polyvalent metal ion (Figs. 2 and 5). This present work also indicates that backbone furnished by guar gum in guar gum-graft-acrylamide may also have role in binding polyvalent metal ion.

Conclusion

Thermograms indicate aqueous solution of water soluble polymers e.g. guar gum and polyacrylamide are producing distinct mass with Cu^{2+} or Y^{3+} when pH is raised. In some cases, slight explosive nature is found probably because of difference in microstructure. This approach supports ion binding by guar gum-graft-acrylamide.

Acknowledgement

Author acknowledges thanks to Professor P. K. Nandi, Professor R. P. Singh and the authority of IIT, Kharagpur for help and co-operation in this regard.

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